

FUTURE MIGRATION
SCENARIOS FOR EUROPE

Report

BULGARIA

Migration and demographic patterns in Central-Eastern Europe

BULGARIA

Migration and demographic patterns in Central-Eastern Europe

Report

Cracow University of Economics, CASPAR

Authors: Natalia Styrnol, Dobrosława Wiktor-Mach, Joanna Sikorska

Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to us at: jan.brzozowski@uek.krakow.pl

ISBN (pdf) 978-91-8001-045-0

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7777280

Funded by the EU Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant ID 870649

Cover photo: Kristin Todorova/Unsplash.com

Layout: Kotryna Juskaite

Report

BULGARIA

Migration and demographic patterns in Central-Eastern Europe

Contents

5	Abstract
6	1. Introduction
10	2. Methodology, Definitions and Sources
13	3. Bulgarian diaspora
17	4. Immigrant stock in Bulgaria
23	5. Immigrant flows in Bulgaria
32	6. Conclusions
33	7. Narrative scenario for Bulgaria
34	7.1 Migration potential for Bulgaria
38	7.2 Migration prospects
40	7.3 Asylum-seekers and refugees
41	7.4 Impact of Covid-19 pandemic
42	References

Picture: Natalya Letunova/Unsplash.com

Abstract

This report is a part of deliverable “D.6.2. Report on migration and demographic patterns in the EU CEE countries and potential source countries” from the project FUME – Future Migration Scenarios for Europe (870649), financed with the Horizon 2020 programme. In particular, this country report focuses on critical analysis of migration data in Bulgaria. The analysis consists of an overview of stock and flow data on migrants, including such dimensions as age groups, gender, country of origin, education levels and length of residence. This report is a first step in analytical exercise of this deliverable which aims to determine migration potential from and to Bulgaria and furthermore, to provide necessary data input for fine-tuning of FUME migration projection model.

The Republic of Bulgaria is a country in Southeast Europe, which joined the European Union in 2007, but so far is outside of the Schengen zone. It has traditionally been a country of emigration, i.e., more Bulgarians used to leave the country than foreign-born persons arrived. In the last decade, immigration has been increasing but, nevertheless, it still remains at a relatively low level in comparison to other EU countries. The report presents a historical overview of migration processes in Bulgaria, underlying mainly recent emigration tendencies. Then, migration stocks and flows are analyzed using mainly national data complemented by research reports. Moreover, the report presents migration data estimations provided by Abel and Cohen (2019).

1. Introduction

Historically, migration processes in Bulgaria were intertwined with the developments inside the Ottoman Empire. That era began a tradition of Bulgarian communities living outside the country of origin. Emigration in the 19th century and at the beginning of the 20th had mostly political (change of borders after the Liberation of Bulgaria in 1878, Balkan wars, First World War), and economic character. According to the 2014 National Strategy for Bulgarian Citizens and Historic Bulgarian Communities, the historic emigration gave rise to Bulgarian communities in Macedonia, Russia, Romania, Greece, Turkey, Serbia, Western Balkans, Moldova, and Ukraine. The members of those 'historic' Bulgarian communities have either foreign or dual citizenship. The legacy of the Cold War era in the migration field is seen in 'old' Bulgarian migrant groups settled mainly in Central and Western Europe, the United States, Canada and Australia. The 2014 Strategy states that the majority of those migrants retained their original citizenship (Vankova 2020: 70-71). On the other hand, the key historic immigration waves into Bulgaria included Armenian refugees from the genocide in the Ottoman empire, foreign students, and economic migrants during the USSR period, (e.g., Vietnamese gastarbeiters in the 1980s) (Krasteva 2006: 26).

Contemporary Bulgaria is mostly an emigration country, taking into account migration flows as well as stocks. It's political, economic and social transformations overlap with a high level of migration dynamics. A key historical factor that changed Bulgaria's recent migration landscape was the collapse of the USSR and the beginning of deep political, economic and socio-cultural changes. A significant wave of emigration occurred just a few months after the fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989. It's described as the 'first emigration period' and had a predominantly political and ethnic nature. Emigrant stock from that time included mainly Bulgarians of Turkish origin who got a chance to escape from discriminatory practices and assimilation campaigns of the Bulgarian government, and, at the same time, to get Turkish citizenship upon settling in Turkey. Due to the mass character of that migration wave, estimated at 300,000, it became known as "the big excursion". According to the UN's data from 1990, 462,767 people in Turkey were born in Bulgaria (Open Society Institute 2017: 2). Some of those people later returned to Bulgaria or emigrated further to other European countries (Bogdanov, Rangelova 2012: 5-6; Rangelova et al., 2006: 43-66; Smilov, Jileva 2009: 220).

In the 1990s, Bulgaria witnessed the second emigration period which lasted till 2001 and, unlike the previous wave, had mostly an economic character. After the centrally planned economy was brought to an end, the society had to struggle with complex implications of an emergent market economy. Transition period was marked by political instability, changing economic policies, and high levels of unemployment. According to the National Statistical Institute, Bulgaria's cumulative GDP fell by more than 30% in the first half of the 1990s, and the unemployment level rose from 1.7% in 1990 to 16.4% three years later (Bogdanov, Rangelova 2012: 3-6). Those processes resulted in a massive emigration which, not compensated by an immigration influx, led to a serious depopulation process (Koyama 2018; Krasteva 2019). The post-1989 migration processes contributed to the formation of the so-called "young" Bulgarian communities abroad, as the aforementioned 2014 Strategy describes them in contrast to older waves (Vankova 2020: 71).

Figure 1. Emigration from Bulgaria, 1989-1996 (border information).

Data source: Kalchev, 2001: 128, 150-2, za: Guentcheva, Kabakchieva, Kolarski, 2003: 16.

The estimates of the scale of emigration differ depending on the methodology. For example, the National Statistical Institute (NSI) provides two divergent emigration data sets for that decade. One of them from that decade includes administrative data from the population censuses from 1992 and 2001, while another – data from border control, showing the number of Bulgarian citizens, older than 16 years old, leaving and entering the country each year, combined with data from special inquiries at 12-15 border crossing points between 1991 and 1996 (a methodology devised by NSI). Comparing the census data reveals that between 1992 and 2001 around 196 000 Bulgarians emigrated from the country and, in the same period, approximately 19 000 immigrated (Guentcheva, Kabakchieva, Kolarski, 2003: 16-17). On the other hand, the latter method based on border information resulted in a different estimation suggesting that for the period 1989-1996 the number of emigrants from Bulgaria was much higher and amounted to 654 000 (Table 1). The discrepancy between the results of different methodologies is significant and, therefore, an awareness of data sources and their limitation is crucial in painting a reliable picture of migration processes in Bulgaria.

In the 1990s also the immigrants' profile changed. New ethnic and national groups began to settle in Bulgaria, e.g. the Chinese. Moreover, existing networks served as a basis for attracting new groups, which resulted in new waves of migrants e.g. from Vietnam, Armenia, Russia, Macedonia. There was also an increase in the number of refugees trying to come to Bulgaria (in 1993 there were 273 applications for a refugee status, whereas in 2002 – 2888) (Krasteva 2006: 27).

Next breakthrough in Bulgaria's migration history occurred due to the European Union accession in 2007. However, already in 2001, the visa-free short visits into the Schengen area were allowed. The post-accession migration processes are typical for most of the new EU member states. The rights to free movement within the EU and an easier, although restricted for a couple of years¹, access to labour markets further encouraged Bulgarians to emigrate, following the pattern of other new EU members. It is difficult to assess the exact impact of EU accession on emigration as the available data do not provide the full picture. The National Institute of Statistics, e.g, presents emigration data for 1992-2011, which led to a conclusion that for that period only 410,472 Bulgarians emigrated. Other sets of official data collected by the Bulgarian State Agency for the Bulgarians Abroad and the Ministry of the Interior showed that, for 2013, approximately 650,000 of Bulgarians live in various EU member countries, 350,000 in the USA and Canada, and 50,000 in Australia, New Zealand and the RPA (Dmitrova, Kahl, 2013: 7-9). Although the figures are just estimations and do not count all emigrants, nevertheless they point to the phenomena of a quite large Bulgarian diaspora scattered all over the world, but predominantly concentrated in Europe. According to the data presented by the NSI in the period of 2007-2011 61,334 persons left Bulgaria and the majority were women and the younger people. At the same time, 13,347 persons immigrated into Bulgaria and, according to the official data, these were Bulgarian citizens who returned to their home country as well as foreign citizens who were granted residence permits. The immigrants came mainly from Turkey (39,4%), Macedonia (5,7%), Greece (5,0%) and Moldova (4,9%) (NSI 2014: 6-7).

The so-called European migration crisis also affected Bulgaria, although to a lesser extent than Western and Southern Europe. The most evident was the rise of a number of Syrians in Bulgaria, as it increased from 792 in 2013 to 11,484 in 2017 (European Commission, Governance of Migrant Integration in Bulgaria).

¹ Bulgarians were granted full access to the EU's labour market in January 2014. Some countries, including most of those which joined the EU in 2004 as well as Sweden and Finland lifted the restrictions already in 2007 (Dąbrowski 2014).

Picture: Yoav Aziz/Unsplash.com

2. Methodology, Definitions and Sources

Methodological approach

This report was based upon a desk research method and critical data analysis. The first step was to gather the main relevant data on immigration numbers (stock and flows) from official sources in Bulgaria and other Central and Eastern European countries belonging to the EU. Data were obtained from state sources, including the Bulgarian National Statistical Institute, reports and surveys on recent migration processes related to the analyzed country. Relevant academic literature and policy papers have also been consulted. The main theme of interest was immigration, but an overview of emigration and a discussion on the diaspora is also included. The research team has therefore paid special attention to existing data on immigrant stocks and flows. The report provides a critical assessment of those data suggesting biases and problems in data collection and reliability. The migration statistics provided by the official Bulgarian sources was finally compared with the estimations on immigrant flows by Abel & Cohen (2019).

Evidencing of migrants in statistical registers and definitions of migrants

In Bulgaria, the main data source for estimating population – including migrants – is census-based. They provide basic statistical data on migration processes and enable to estimate the volume of international migration. The most recent are from 1985, 1992, 2001, and 2011. Since the next census is planned for 2021, the last complete figures are quite old. Nevertheless, the National Statistical Institute presents some estimates of international migration since 2007. The data is reported with breakdowns by several variables, such as age and sex, country of birth and citizenship (National Statistical Institute, 2014, 2020e). Some of those data are not, however, publicly available and had to be obtained by personal communication with the NSI's staff.

Migration stocks

Data provided by the Bulgarian National Statistical Institute on migrant stocks includes information on two categories of immigrants: a) foreign-born population and b) people having foreign citizenship. There are also separate data sets on the number of third-country nationals holders of long-term or permanent residence permits.

The definitions used by the NSI are as follows:

Immigrants: "Persons who have changed their usual residence abroad with a residence in Bulgaria and who have resided or have an intention to reside more than 12 months at the country territory."

Emigrants: "Persons who have changed their usual residence in Bulgaria with a residence abroad and who have been absent or have an intention to be absent from the country for more than 12 months period" (Eurostat 2017).

Those definitions imply that migration statistics will mostly include information on long-term migrants who are legally staying in Bulgaria and have their residence place officially registered by relevant authorities.

Third-country nationals: "persons who are not citizens of the European Union". They are entitled to three types of a residence permit in Bulgaria: prolonged (up to 1 year), long-term (initial 5 years term permitted) and permanent. Data source on residence permits comes from the Bulgarian Ministry of Interior, Register for Foreigners. Data on this group of immigrants granted residence permits is disaggregated by duration and reason for stay (National Statistical Institute, Methodology on Statistics and Residence Permits).

Migration flows

Bulgarian National Statistical Institute provides publicly available data on international migration for the time period of 2012 – 2019. It defines a migrant (referred to as a 'migrated person') as a person who has changed their residence (measured by address data). The data on migration is gathered during the moment of migration and is calculated once a year. An international migration refers to the fact of "the change of usual residence in Bulgaria with a residence abroad or vice versa." Therefore, the yearly calculation and the number presented in the official state statistics of migration flows encompasses all people that crossed the border – both entered and left Bulgaria, i.e., inflow and outflow - and changed their address, which implies a longer-term stay (National Statistical Institute, Metadata and Methodology). The numbers are collected on the basis of personal declarations and, therefore, these figures do not include persons who did not register at the administrative authorities in Bulgaria (i.e., retain residency of their home countries). Neither do they include those migrants who came for a shorter period of time (i.e., temporary or seasonal workers). As a result, we can assume, the data sets on migration stocks and flows are underestimated.

In Bulgaria, registration is obligatory on arrival, but there is no obligation to de-register when leaving the country. Only incentives exist and the time limit is not specified (Eurostat 2015), so the quality of data may not be satisfactory.

Immigration flow - interpreted by the Bulgarian authorities as the fact of a change of one's address abroad with an address in Bulgaria - refer basically to two categories to people. This movement includes both Bulgarian citizens, i.e. return migrants, and people having citizenship of other countries who have been granted residence permit or status (National Statistical Institute, 2020e).

Another problem with evidencing the real scale of migrant flows is the issue of undocumented migrants. Due to its strategic location, Bulgaria became in recent years the entrance point to European Union.

The turning point was 2013 when many immigrants began to arrive at Bulgarian territory with the hope of continuing the journey further to more affluent European countries. It's difficult to assess the number of these groups, since many migrate illegally, and the only data are on the number of migrants detected by the Border Police. The trend of an increase of detected cases is, however, visible. The most common countries of origin of undocumented migrants are: Iraq, Afghanistan, Syria, Pakistan, and Iran (IOM 2016).

Ethnic Bulgarian - a channel for immigrant entry into Bulgaria

Other key concepts include “people of Bulgarian origin” and “foreign Bulgarians”. Current migration policy priorities include encouraging emigrants and people of Bulgarian origin to return or settle back in the country of origin of their ancestors. That policy dates back to the 1990s when a number of new regulations were proposed. The notions which refer to the ethnicity came to be used in migration policy debates as the country was experiencing population decline and development challenges. People included in those categories get preferential access to citizenship, which was already included in the 1991 Constitution. Ethnic Bulgarians are given rights to a “facilitated procedure” (art. 25(2)) in obtaining Bulgarian citizenship (Smilov, Jileva 2009: 220).

The approach of Bulgarian public institutions towards Bulgarian emigrants can be seen in a number of documents and political instruments which form a basis for the diaspora policy and engagement with compatriots living in other countries. The key documents include: the 1991 Constitution, the 2000 Law on the Bulgarians living outside the Republic of Bulgaria, Law on Bulgarian Citizenship from 1998, the 2014 National Strategy for Bulgarian Citizens and Historic Bulgarian Communities and the 2015 National Strategy in the field of Migration, Asylum and Integration (Koch 2020; Vankova 2020: 70). They basically aim at facilitating integration of members of Bulgarian diaspora with the Bulgarians in the homeland. Those documents introduce, among others, definitions applied to various groups of Bulgarians which are of interest to the state, which have implications for the methodology in the migration area. According to the 200 Law on the Bulgarians living outside the Republic of Bulgaria this group refers to people having particular characteristics: “have at least one relative of Bulgarian origin in their ascending line, possess Bulgarian national consciousness, and resides permanently on the territory of another state” (Vankova 2020: 70).

3. Bulgarian diaspora

Assessing the scale of the Bulgarian diaspora is not an easy task due to the lack of comprehensive, reliable and systematic data, and, therefore, there are various claims in this topic. It is also difficult to assess Bulgarian diaspora in numbers since many people do not register their address in a host country neither at local authorities nor at diplomatic missions. Existing data are based more on estimations than on empirical facts (Angelov, Lessenski, 2017).

According to censuses from other countries (receiving countries), in 2011 there were around 1 million people who had been born in Bulgaria (Open Society Institute, 2017). These data, however, have many drawbacks, e.g., they reflect only registered people, and they are relatively old. Then next censuses in most European countries are scheduled for 2021.

The National Strategy for Bulgarian Citizens and Historic Bulgarian Communities from 2014 estimates that there were approximately 3-3,5 millions of Bulgarians living abroad. Out of them around 2 million possess Bulgarian citizenship (Vankova 2020: 71).

Picture: Anton Atanasov/Unsplash.com

The Ministry of Foreign Affairs in 2019 presented their estimations, according to which more than 2,2 million of Bulgarian citizens dwell in other countries. According to their data, the top destination countries are Germany (416,000), Turkey (350,000), the United States and Greece (in each of them the number is around 300,000), Spain (250,000), and the United Kingdom (200,000). Smaller communities are located in Italy, Canada, France, Austria, Cyprus, the Czech Republic, the Republic of South Africa, Switzerland and in many other countries. The data are gathered from diplomatic missions and election registers ("Ponad 2,2 mln Bułgarów żyje za granicą", 2019).

According to the latest data for 2019 provided by the NSI the majority of emigrants are the young people - 49% are between 20-39 years. The youngest emigrants (under 20 years) constitute almost 19% of all who left. The top destination countries, according to 2019 data, were: Germany (20,3%), the United Kingdom (17,7%), and Italy (13,5%) (National Statistical Institute, 2020e)

Emigration data available for Bulgaria is, however, not complete and thus not reliable. The figures collected and presented by the NSI refer only to the "official" data. They cover only the cases of Bulgarian citizens who had lived in Bulgaria and now reside legally in another country. Moreover, according to the methodology adopted by NSI, an emigrant is a person who resides outside of Bulgaria for at least 12 months (NSI, Methodology). This approach leaves a significant group of temporary and circular migrants, who work abroad only for a short period of time and often have not registered their stay abroad and often work illegally. Besides, such groups as the children of migrants, e.g., the "second generation" who may still have Bulgarian citizenship are not included in the official data (c.f., Dąbrowski 2014; Dmitrova, Kahl, 2013:7). Some researchers also add another factor influencing the difficulty in obtaining a precise picture of emigration, i.e., the NSI only counts those Bulgarian citizens who have notified the authorities of their new residence place, which is not often the case (Bogdanov & Rangelova, 2012: 5).

It is important to note that the Bulgarian diaspora policy is linked to its migration and population priorities. One of the key aims is to attempt to encourage Bulgarian emigrants and people having Bulgarian origin to settle back in Bulgaria. It is seen as a tool to overcome the ongoing demographic processes - in particular the population decline of recent decades (Vankova, 2020).

Figure 2. Emigration from Bulgaria 2007-2019. Emigrants with Bulgarian citizenship, emigrants with foreign citizenship.

Source: National Statistical Institute (2020b).

According to the latest data for 2019 provided by the NSI the majority of emigrants are the young people - 49% are between 20-39 years. The youngest emigrants (under 20 years) constitute almost 19% of all who left.

Picture: Georgi Kyurpanov/Unsplash.com

4. Immigrant stock in Bulgaria

According to the last census, there were 36 723 persons with foreign citizenship that lived in Bulgaria permanently as of 1st February 2011, which amounted to 0,5% of the country's population. Most of them lived in urban areas (83%) and more than half (56%) were women (National Statistical Institute 2011a: 21).

Half of the number of persons (50,6%) with foreign citizenship living permanently in Bulgaria come from European countries that are not European Union member-states. Holders of Russian citizenship prevailed in the group described (11 991 persons - 65,1% of non- EU country citizens). The second biggest group consisted of Ukrainian citizens (3 064 - 16,6%), and Macedonian (1 091 - 5,9%), Moldovan (893- 4,8%) and Serbian (569 - 3,1%) followed (Ibidem).

Concerning European Union citizens living in Bulgaria in 2011, the number amounted to 8444 persons. The largest group consisted of the UK citizens (2605 persons - 30,9% of all the EU citizens living in Bulgaria). The Greek citizenship holders (1 253 - 14,8%), German (848 - 10%), Polish (819 - 9,7%), and Italian (456 - 5,4%) were other considerably big groups of foreigners (Ibid.: 22).

Immigrants with an Asian country citizenship constituted a share of 22,9% (8403 persons) (National Statistical Institute, 2011b) of all the foreigners living in Bulgaria permanently in 2011. The Turkish, Armenian, and Chinese citizens were the biggest groups among the Asians - 32,6%, 13,9% and 8,9% respectively (National Statistical Institute, 2011a: 22).

Foreigners holding citizenship of countries of other continents (Africa, South America, North America, Oceania) constituted a much smaller share of the group described here- 3,9% of all foreigners (1417 persons) registered in the 2011 Census (National Statistical Institute 2011b) (Figure 3.).

Figure 3. Persons with foreign citizenship living in Bulgaria by continents (data as of 1.02.2011)

Source: National Statistical Institute (2011b).

All the continents taken into account, the feminization ratio was the highest among European country citizenship holders and amounted to 64,1%. It was even higher considering European countries outside the European Union - 74,2%. Groups of Belarussian, Ukrainian and Russian citizens were the most feminized ones concerning non EU member countries (feminization ratio equals 82,1%, 80,7% and 79% respectively) (National Statistical Institute 2011b).

Figure 4. Feminization ratio of the foreign population by continents (data for 01.02.2011)
Source: National Statistical Institute (2011b).

The authors of the Census 2011 report have also highlighted the number of double citizenship holders: Persons who have declared double citizenship at the census moment - Bulgarian and others are 22 152 or 0.3% of the country population. Amongst them, highest is the share of persons with Bulgarian and Russian citizenship - 5 257 (23.7%), followed by persons with Bulgarian and Turkish citizenship - 4 282 (19.3%), Bulgarian and citizenship of the USA - 1 725 (7.8%) (National Statistical Institute 2011a: 22).

Data on the population registered by the National Statistical Institute available online and the data provided to us by the NSI officers allow us to analyze the changes in immigrant stocks in Bulgaria since 2012. There is a significant difference between the number of foreigners registered by citizenship and between the number of foreign-born persons. There is a constant growth in terms of the numbers of people with foreign citizenship residing in Bulgaria, and also in terms of the number of people that were born outside of the country.

Persons who have declared double citizenship at the census moment - Bulgarian and others are 22 152 or 0.3% of the country population. Amongst them, highest is the share of persons with Bulgarian and Russian citizenship - 5 257 (23.7%), followed by persons with Bulgarian and Turkish citizenship - 4 282 (19.3%), Bulgarian and citizenship of the USA - 1 725 (7.7%)

Among all foreign citizenship holders, the most numerous group was the Russians, whose population has been growing constantly since 2012. The population in 2019 was more than two times larger than at the beginning of the data registration (2012). Another group that is growing dynamically is the one comprising Turkish citizens. Although the Turkish population is smaller than the Russian one, the number of citizens of that country has enlarged four times in the period of 2012-2019. Moreover, 2014 was the year when Syrian citizens started to appear very clearly in the Bulgarian migration statistics. The population of Syrians residing in Bulgaria grew almost twice since 2014. Also, citizenship holders of Ukraine, Great Britain and Greece have appeared in the statistics as the most numerous groups of foreigners in the respective years. The numbers of Ukrainian migrants are rising steadily, and a similar but less dynamic process is observable concerning migration of the British. Data about the Greek citizens appeared in the dataset (that focuses on the most numerous groups of migrants only) concerning only the years of 2012 and 2013 (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Population of foreigners registered by citizenship in comparison with foreign-born population
Source: National Statistical Institute (2020c).

Figure 6. Population by non-Bulgarian citizens as of 31.12. of the respective year - the most numerous groups
Source: National Statistical Institute (2020b).

The largest groups of migrants registered in 2019 consisted of the Russians, the Turkish and the Syrians. However, the migrant population of these countries varied significantly in terms of feminization levels. As pictured by the Figure 7., the group, among those three, that is displaying the highest share of women in the entire population residing in Bulgaria concerning the 2012-2019 period, is composed of Russian Federation citizens. Quite opposite characteristics are observable in the group of Turkish citizens, where men constitute a clearly dominant part of the whole migrant population, although the share of women is slowly rising (Figure 8.). Syrian migration to Bulgaria is much more balanced in terms of feminization/masculinization than the Russian and Turkish ones. Still, the number of Syrian men remains higher than the number of Syrian women in the Syrian population residing in Bulgaria (Figure 9.).

Figure 7. Russian citizenship holders by sex
Source: National Statistical Institute (2020b).

Figure 8. Turkish citizenship holders by sex
Source: National Statistical Institute (2020b).

Figure 9. Syrian citizenship holders by sex
 Source: National Statistical Institute (2020b).

Figure 10. Population of non-Bulgarian citizenship holders by age in 2019
 Source: National Statistical Institute (2020c).

The most recent data available on the age structure of the migrant population in 2019 shows that cohorts of persons aged 30-39, 40-49, 50-59 and 60-69 constitute the largest groups of all the immigrants with foreign citizenship in Bulgaria. Generally, the middle-aged and older generations are most represented among migrants, which stands in stark contrast to e.g., the Polish situation where the majority of migrants are young

Another source of information about the immigrant stocks in Bulgaria is the data about the number of third country nationals holders of long-term or permanent residence as of 31.12. of the respective year (Table 1.). Data available on the 2014-2019 period present a constant growth of the immigrant stocks, with almost a double increase of the number of residence permits holders in 2017.

Table 1. The number of third-country nationals holders of long-term/permanent residence permit
Source: National Statistical Institute (2020d).

Year	Third-country nationals holders of long term/permanent residence permit (number)
2014 ²	971
2015	13670
2016	16205
2017	31587
2018	33524
2019	45236

² Data for 2014 was accessed in April 2020 and is not anymore available in December 2020

Picture: Dimitar Kazakov/Unsplash.com

5. Immigrant flows in Bulgaria

Estimating international migration flows is not an easy task and it is difficult to get reliable data which can give us a precise picture of movement of people across borders. In the case of Bulgaria, one of the factors affecting its migration patterns is the EU membership since 2007, which increases the country's attractiveness. At the same time, Bulgaria is still not inside the Schengen zone which also affects the free movement of people, and this fact may influence potential immigrants' strategies.

One of the datasets on international migration available at the NSI database includes only the persons who changed their address abroad with an address in Bulgaria (as of the 31.12. of the reference year). Yearly inflows of migrants have grown significantly since 2007, the year when the country joined European Union what is clearly depicted by Figure 11. below.

Figure 11. Immigration to Bulgaria - total, Bulgarian citizens and non-Bulgarian citizenship holders (2007-2019)
Source: National Statistical Institute (2020a, 2020b).

Immigrants with foreign citizenship outnumbered Bulgarian return migrants in the period of 2012-2016. However, in the years 2007-2011 and 2017-2019 Bulgarian citizens constituted the bigger share of all the immigrants in the year given and their participation in the immigrant inflow has been growing in recent years. In 2019, they constituted 62% of total immigration to Bulgaria.

Growth of the share of foreign-citizenship holders in the immigration flows during 2012-2016 period is due to the increasing Syrian, Russian, Turkish and Ukrainian immigration (Figure 12.). Other, less numerous groups of migrants also contributed to the rising immigration to Bulgaria. Greece and the United Kingdom were among the top countries of origin during that period of time - in 2012 Greek citizens were the second largest group of foreign immigrants in Bulgaria (1440 persons), just after the Russians (2020b).

Figure 12. Immigration of persons holding non-Bulgarian citizenship
Source: National Statistical Institute (2020b).

From less than one hundred registered immigrants with foreign citizenship in 2007 and 2008, the numbers grew to more than 14 thousand in 2019, which is 228 times more than at the beginning of this registry. Turkish citizens were the only group of immigrants present in the top countries of origin in these statistics every year. They constituted the most numerous group of foreigners in 2007, 2010-2011, 2013 and in the period of 2017-2019. Russian citizenship holders were also an important group in terms of numbers. Most of them, 3903 persons, migrated to Bulgaria in 2014, when the overall immigration flow in Bulgaria was the highest. Another group of non-European country citizenship holders that became a significantly large one, comprised of Syrian migrants, whose numbers were increasing until 2014 and stayed in the topmost numerous immigrant groups until 2018.

Concerning the legalization of stay of the third-country nationals, most of the permits of residence³ have been issued due to family reasons. Russian, Turkish and Ukrainian citizenship are the most numerous groups in this category. Interestingly, Chinese and the USA citizens appear among the largest groups as well, although the number of permits issued to them has been few times smaller than to the citizens of the three aforementioned countries (Table 2.).

*Table 2. Permits of residence issued yearly due to family reasons
Source: National Statistical Institute (2020b).*

Citizenship	2015	Citizenship	2016	Citizenship	2017	Citizenship	2018	Citizenship	2019
Total	2906	Total	3240	Total	3615	Total	3792	Total	4097
Russia	781	Russia	768	Turkey	1039	Turkey	1173	Turkey	1243
Turkey	597	Turkey	733	Russia	843	Russia	753	Russia	786
Ukraine	485	Ukraine	514	Ukraine	416	Ukraine	418	Ukraine	525
China	91	China	103	USA	94	USA	108	USA	114
Kazakhstan	77	USA	96	China	91	China	97	China	111
Other countries	875	Other countries	1026	Other countries	1132	Other countries	1243	Other countries	1318

³ The first residence permit issued to a third-country national in the respective year is concerned here. By definition, the first residence permit is a residence permit issued to a person, a third-country national for the first time, as well as one issued after at least 6 months after the expiry of the transitional permit (National Statistical Institute 2020f).

The number of residence permits issued to the third-country nationals due to reasons linked with work, education and other premises has been mostly increasing in the period of 2015-2019 (Figure 13.). Most permits issued by reason of work were granted to Turkish, Russian and Ukrainian citizens, except for 2016, when the number of documents dropped significantly (from 2261 in 2015 to 276 in 2016). In 2016, the USA citizens were the largest group of persons granted residence permits due to work reasons (85 immigrants). Also, Indian citizens appeared in that registry in 2016 - 12 of them were granted a residence permit but the number increased rapidly in 2017 when 222 Indian citizenship holders obtained that document. Other less numerous groups appearing in those statistics (but still the top largest ones) consisted of the Chinese (all the years in the period of 2015-2019, except for 2017), the Northern Macedonians (2015, 2017) and the Serbians (2017-2019) (National Statistical Institute 2020b).

The overall number of residence permits issued on the education premises has been generally lower than concerning other reasons. Here, the Turkish were the most numerous group in all the years apart from 2019. The Northern Macedonians were the second largest one (except for 2015 when they were the third biggest group) and the Ukrainian citizens followed in terms of number. Only in 2019 they constituted the largest group of third-country nationals who were granted the residence permit on the education premises. Citizens of Serbia, Nigeria and India also appear in that registry but the number of permits issued to them rarely surpassed 100 per year.

Figure 13. Number of residence permits issued yearly to the third-country nationals due to various reasons, 2015-2019
Source: National Statistical Institute (2020b).

Asylum seekers are a relatively large group of foreigners arriving in the Republic of Bulgaria. They are therefore contributing to immigration flows in that country, even though the country grants much less refugee statuses and subsidiary protection statuses than other European Union states - 11% and 19% respectively (Savova 2020: 11). The number of applications for international protection submitted had its peak in 2015 - it amounted to 20391 but dropped drastically in 2017 and in November 2020 it equaled only 2986.

Figure 14. Number of applications for international protection submitted yearly, 01.01.1993- 30.11.2020
 Source: State Agency for Refugees with the Council of Ministers (2020a).

Figure 15. Number of refugee status and subsidiary protection granted yearly, 01.01.1993- 30.11.2020
 Source: State Agency for Refugees with the Council of Ministers (2020a).

Most of the refugee statuses were granted in 2014 (5162) and 2015 (4708). Despite a very high number of applications in 2016 (19418), comparable to the one in the previous year (20391), the number of refugee statuses granted dropped to only 764.

The Afghans, the Syrians and the Iraqis have been the most numerous groups of asylum seekers applying for international protection in Bulgaria since 1993, the beginning of the registry and persist to be the largest groups until 2020.

Figure 16. Top countries of origin of the asylum seekers in Bulgaria, 1993-2019

Source: State Agency for Refugees with the Council of Ministers (2020b).

Concerning 2019, Asylum Information Database provides detailed information about the characteristics of the group of applicants and persons who were granted an international protection status. Most of the asylum seekers in 2019 (similarly to the whole period of 1993-2020) originated from Afghanistan (997 out of 2152 - 46,3%), Syria (487 applicants - 22,6% of all) and from Iraq (303 persons - 14,1% of all the applicants). The rejection rate of applications differs depending on the nationality, however - even though the Afghans were the most numerous group of asylum seekers in 2019, only 6% of them were granted either a refugee status or subsidiary protection status (rejection rate equaled 94%). The situation was different for the Syrians, whose only 3 % of applications were rejected. Concerning the third largest group of asylum seekers - the Iraqis- the rejection rate of their applications amounted to 82 % in 2019 (Savova 2020: 7).

The applicants for the refugee status in 2019 in Bulgaria consisted mostly of men - the masculinization ratio equalled 86% (of all adults). Children constituted 9% of all asylum seekers and unaccompanied minors - 24% of the applicants for the international protection (Savova 2020: 8).

Although persons granted a refugee status or subsidiary protection status constituted relatively large group of foreigners in Bulgaria, especially in some years (i.e., 2014, 2015), and have been influencing the migration picture in Bulgaria, there is no information available at the National Statistical Institute, whether they are counted into the group of international migrants, or not.

Table 3. International migration of non-Bulgarian citizens, 2011-2015
Source: National Statistical Institute (2020a, 2020b).

Year	Number of international immigrants
2011	2029
2012	9139
2013	13888
2014	17133
2015	14501
Total 2011-2015	56670

One of the aims of the report is also to compare the national statistics with the estimations of bilateral international migration flows by Abel and Cohen (2019). The latest dataset analyzed by the authors came from the United Nations Population Division (UNCPD) and covers the 5-year period between 2011 and 2015. According to their estimates, around 21,5 thousand people immigrated to Bulgaria. The most numerous groups of migrants came from Russia (5159), Romania (1666), Ukraine (1619), Greece (1359), Turkey (1090).

The immigration flows presented in this report show, however, that Abel and Cohen's calculations are largely underestimated and, therefore, not very useful for examining the migration processes in Bulgaria nor for predicting future trends. The data available at the NSI database, which pictures only the minimum number of international migrants in Bulgaria (since the persons considered are only those who registered their change of residence address), show that the scale of international migration is more than twice bigger than in Abel and Cohen's calculations.

Abel and Cohen's calculations were correct in terms of defining the most numerous group of immigrants - the Russian citizens. The number, however, appears to be largely underestimated - according to the NSI data, there were 12,6 thousand of Russians who arrived in Bulgaria in the period of 2011-2015, which is more than twice more than stated in the Abel and Cohen's dataset. The second largest group of immigrants were the Syrians (not the Romanian citizens) - there were 10,9 thousand of them registered between 2011 and 2015. The third largest group, according to the NSI statistics, consisted of the Turkish with 9,9 thousand immigrants registered. According to Abel and Cohen's estimations, there should be only 1090 of them in Bulgaria during the referred period of time. Lastly, the Ukrainian immigrants that constitute the fourth largest group of foreigners in the period of 2011-2015, according to the NSI data, are the third biggest one in Abel and Cohen's estimations. It is not a correct piece of information, taking as a point of reference the official Bulgarian migration statistics.

Table 4. Comparison of the data on immigration in the period of 2011-2015: National Statistical Institute and Abel and Cohen's estimations

Source: National Statistical Institute (2020a, 2020b), Abel & Cohen (2019).

Country of origin	NSI Data	Abel and Cohen's dataset
Russian Federation	12 602	5159
Syria	10 952	345
Turkey	9901	1090
Ukraine	2625	1619

Picture: Jean Carlo Emer/Unsplash.com

6. Conclusions

Bulgaria is an example of a European country which has continued to be an emigrant country for at least the last three decades. Since the 1980s large waves of people have left Bulgaria, first due to political, later - mostly economic reasons. Immigration has so far not been significant when it comes to the relative numbers, even though the country is an EU member. However, in recent years Bulgaria gradually begins to attract not only Bulgarian citizens or people of Bulgarian origin, but also third-country nationals and people seeking international protection. Since 2014 Bulgaria has become a home for an increasing number of Syrian citizens. Moreover, in the period 2015-2019, there was a significant rise in the number of residence permits issued to third-country nationals to work, study or related to other reasons. If the immigration trend continues, Bulgaria may transform itself into a country attractive for economic migrants and follow the path of some Central European countries.

The report underlines the difficulties in presenting a realistic overview of migration processes and patterns in the case of Bulgaria due to several problems. The data available publicly are not comprehensive nor detailed enough. Moreover, data on the number of international migrants are collected on the basis of declarations. They are limited to the official registers of people who have changed their address of residence. The statistics do not contain information on temporary or seasonal workers. Consequently, they are underestimated and there is a need to provide additional surveys to fulfil the gaps.

Picture: Maria Teneva/Unsplash.com

7. Narrative scenario for Bulgaria

In this chapter, we will focus on the existing migration potential of Bulgaria as a sending and host country. We will consider the analysis of important push and pull factors. We will take into account such dimensions as demographic structure, economy, technology, social attitudes, governance indicators and existing cultural, economic and geographical bilateral relations with important sending and host countries. As such, these scenario narratives do not aim to foresee the migration future of Bulgaria, but rather to outline the possible future directions of demographic processes, including international migration movements.

7.1 Migration potential for Bulgaria

In this section, we focus on the migration potential of Bulgaria, taking into account six dimensions, namely: demography, economy, technological development, society, governance and environment. The introduced aspects are components of the narrative scenario for Bulgaria.

In the beginning, it must be noted that Bulgarian society is ageing. By the end of 2019, the number of persons aged 65 and over amounted to 21.6 % of the overall population - 25.1 % for females and 17.9 % for males (National Statistical Institute, hereafter NSI, 2020: 2). Also, in recent years Bulgarian population has been slowly decreasing. For instance, in 2012 its number equated to 7.3 million and in 2021 – 6.9 million (Eurostat, 2021a). The annual number of deaths during the last two decades oscillated between 105 thousand and 125 thousand (NSI, 2021a).

For a decade the life expectancy at birth remains unchanged and equates to 74 years - 71 for males and 78 for females (NSI, 2021b). At the same time, the fertility rate in Bulgaria has been insignificantly growing from 1.50 in 2011 to 1.58 in 2019 (Eurostat, 2021b), though still remains low.

According to the Bulgarian National Statistical Institute (NSI), emigration outbalanced immigration events over the last ten years. The emigration trend remains major, the Bulgarian state hosts more and more newcomers. For instance, in 2010 the number of emigration events totalled 27.7 thousand and immigration events – 3.5 thousand (NSI, 2021c). In 2019 the outflow from Bulgaria amounted to 39.9 thousand persons, while in turn 37.9 thousand persons came to the state (Ibidem). Importantly, the immigration flow has increased even after the Covid-19 outbreak, when the statistics showed that in 2020 nearly 6.5 thousand persons left Bulgaria due to limited mobility or even immobility, and at the same time, 37.3 immigrants arrived in the country (NSI, 2021c).

According to the official statistics, the largest share of the third-country nationals in Bulgaria arrived in the country for other reasons than economic activity, family or education (see: Figure 13). The number of the 'other reason' group in 2018 equated to 5.1 thousand, in 2019 – 5.4 thousand and in 2020 – 3.8 thousand. The second-largest migrant group regarded by reasons of stay concerns family ties. The number of family migrants in 2018 totalled 3.8 thousand, in 2019 – 4 thousand and in 2020 - 9 thousand. When it comes to the third-country nationals motivated by the economic reasons, their number amounted to 1.6 thousand in 2018, – 2.4 thousand in 2019 and 2.4 thousand in 2020. In turn, the number of migrants that arrived in Bulgaria due to educational reasons amounted to 1.3 thousand in 2018, – 1.6 thousand in 2019 and 1.2 thousand in 2020 (NSI, 2021d). The variety of reasons for stay is evidence of attractiveness of Bulgaria for migrants.

Over the last three decades, Bulgaria has transitioned from a highly centralized and planned economy to an open market and part of the European Union (World Bank, 2021a). In this process, the economic growth has been, however, impaired by the insufficiency in the labour force and educational attainment in the overall population. Currently, the trend of a relatively low education level is changing among the youngest groups. Between 2008 and 2018, the share of primary and lower education graduates decreased by over 6 percentage points. In turn, the share of upper secondary and tertiary education graduates rose by 54 % and 25 %, respectively (Dimitrov et al., 2019: 35).

Also, the employment structure in Bulgaria has been changing. Between 2008 and 2018 the share of employees in the industry, construction, manufacturing, agriculture and education has decreased in favour of the increase in such sectors as services, trade and repair of vehicles, information and communication, transport, administration and scientific and technical activities (Dimitrov et al., 2019: 47-48). In 2019 manufacturing branch was the largest source of employment attracting nearly 19 % of the working population, both males and females. The second group is the trade and repair of vehicles sector which in 2019 employed 16.7 % of the working-age population. The third-largest sector, construction, employed 7.7 % of them (NSI, 2021e). Another

group appearing in the statistics was the agricultural sector, which in 2019 contributed to 3.7 % of the annual GDP (OECD, 2021a: 6) whilst 6.6 % of the working-age population has been employed there (NSI, 2021e).

An important factor to discuss is the participation of the 45-65 years old population in the labour market. An increase in the working population in these age groups occurred between 2010 and 2017. It happened, however, at the expense of a decrease in the younger population's participation in the labour market (Dimitrov et al., 2019: 34). This shift mainly stems from demographic factors (such as low birth rates in recent years) and emigration flows (Ibidem, p. 32). It can be presumed that simultaneously with leaving the labour market by the current working population aged 45-65, immigrant workers will be needed due to labour shortages. Therefore, in the following decades, Bulgaria will experience the demand for the foreign labour force.

In 2018 Bulgaria achieved the lowest unemployment rate in the history of the country which equalled 5.3 % (Ibidem, p. 50). The lowest unemployment rates were demonstrated among age groups between 45- and 54-years old (4.4 %) and among females in general. At the same time, the highest unemployment was observed within the 25-34 age group (6.2 %), which is a score below the EU average (8%) for the same age group (Ibidem, p. 52). Considering the education variable, the unemployment rate is the highest among the primary and lower secondary education graduates which constituted 22.5 % of the unemployed population in 2018, while the score for the EU amounted to 13.7 % (Ibidem, p. 53). It suggests the problems of the labour market inclusiveness in terms of immigration flows, taking into account that the migrant population tends to be hired in low-qualification jobs. It may result in the high unemployment of the potential immigrant population and their presence in the informal economy.

Simultaneously with the economic growth, the share of high-technology economic activities in production will tend to grow. In the following decades, as the young working-age population will enter the labour market, increased labour productivity will be achieved (Dimitrov et al., 2019: 35). As mentioned before, the share of the population with a higher education degree has significantly increased from 18 % to nearly 25 % between 2008 and 2018 (Dimitrov et al., 2019: 35). This trend is promising in terms of a possibly facilitated implementation of the advanced technologies in the future. However, if the level of Bulgarian citizens achieving higher education will not continue increasing, the labour market for the high-qualified immigrants will open more broadly.

The next important point to discuss is the social structure of Bulgaria. While analysing the potential of migration inflows into Bulgaria, we need to consider the presence of ethnic, national, and religious minorities. The status of minorities and attitudes toward immigrants are important factors that need to be considered while assessing international migration movements (de Jong & Boissonneault 2020: 11).

According to the 2011 Population Census in Bulgaria, there are twelve minorities present in the country: Turks, Roma, Russians, Armenians, Vlachs, Macedonians, Greeks, Ukrainians, Jews, Romanians, Tatars and Gagauz (Minority Rights Group, 2018a).

The Turks were the largest minority in 2011 and constituted 8.8 % of the overall population, which amounted to ca. 648 thousand persons (Minority Rights Group, 2018a). Due to hostile historical relations with Bulgarians and current political tensions between centre-right populist Bulgarian party called Citizens for the European Development of Bulgaria (hereafter GERB⁴), the Patriotic Front (PF) and minority-oriented Turkish Movement for Rights and Freedoms (DPS), the question on the place of the Turkish diaspora in the Bulgarian society arose. The tensions regard introducing obligatory Turkish language classes for ethnic Turks, allowing the use of the Turkish language during the public election campaigning and PF's goal to exclude Bulgarian diaspora in Turkey from voting (Minority Rights Group, 2018b).

⁴ Bulg. ГЕРБ, which literally means 'coat of arms'

Despite political competition between political groups, it cannot be assumed that the Bulgarian Turks may leave the country since the 1990s. At that time, Bulgaria implemented the series of rights for the Turkish minority due to their mass outflow to Turkey during the 1980s. Since then, Bulgarian Turks have been allowed to choose their Turkish names, speak Turkish in private conversations and cultivate Islamic festivities and customs (Minority Rights Group, 2018b).

The second-largest minority in Bulgaria consists of the Roma. According to the 2011 Population Census, nearly 361 thousand respondents identified themselves as Roma, which constituted 4.9 % of the overall population (Minority Rights Group, 2018a). However, according to other governmental surveys, the group's number may extend to even 10 % of the overall population since sometimes Roma members identify as Bulgarians, Turks or Romanians (Minority Rights Group, 2018c). Bulgaria still faces some obstacles with Roma integration in terms of education, employment, health and housing. Although some governmental reforms have been introduced, several problems with their implementation have occurred (Minority Rights Group, 2018c).

According to OECD, over 60 % of Romanis aged 15-29 does not participate in the labour market and education which is over three times higher score than among the Bulgarians (OECD, 2021b: 2). The Covid-19 pandemic additionally propelled discrimination against Romanis, especially during the national lockdown. It manifested, for instance, in strict guarding by the police which applied only to the Roma-majority neighbourhoods. Moreover, in many cases, the authorities failed to provide access to food, water and medicaments for the confined groups. Also, hostile anti-Roma rhetoric has been present in the political discourse, implying that Romanis are a collective threat to the general population which resulted in hate speech and public aversion to the Roma community (Amnesty International, 2021: 100).

Opinions about immigrants, especially refugees, are rather unfavourable in Bulgarian society. According to the poll conducted in September 2015 by the Bulgarian sociological agency Alpfa Research, 63 % of the respondents considered refugees as a threat and 78 % perceived refugees as a burden to the economy (Ivanova, 2018: 8). According to another survey conveyed in 2016, 47 % of adult respondents claimed the EU should not help asylum seekers because newcomers can be dangerous and should take refuge in the region of their origin. Other arguments against receiving refugees have been related to the Islamophobic narrative (Kyuchukov, 2016: 5).

As a result of the structural corruption and numerous scandals involving the most important politicians e.g., the leak of a picture of the Prime Minister laying on the pile of money⁵ and the investigation in the independent president's office after which he called for the resignation of the government and the Attorney General, the social protests started in summer 2020. The demonstrators demanded new election and demission of the PM and his government (Pieńkowski, 2020). However, the Bulgarian demonstrators did not hope for a spectacular change as they did not see a real alternative for the GERB party (Ibidem). In the light of these facts, structural corruption and political oligarchy probably will continue to impact the immigrants in the aspects of entrepreneurship and bureaucracy.

After the massive demonstrations calling for PM's resignation that took place in Sofia and major European cities where the Bulgarian diaspora lives (e.g., Brussels, Paris, London, Berlin), the parliamentary elections in Bulgaria were conducted in April 2021. As the winning GERB party could not create the parliamentary majority and no other party was not willing to rule in the coalition, early parliamentary elections were conducted in July 2021. As a result, the election won the anti-corruption and anti-establishment party called There is such a People (ITN), led by the musician Slavi Trifonov. The parliamentary change is a manifestation of the social demand for it. The second-largest number of votes won the coalition of Citizens for the European Development of Bulgaria - Union of Democratic Forces (GEBR-SDS). Also, the Bulgarian Socialist Party (BSP), Turkish Movement for Rights and Freedoms and anti-corruption fraction called "Stand Up.BG! We are coming!" became a part of the coalition (Seroka, 2021).

⁵ Later Borisov claimed the photograph has been falsified.

Picture: Gabriella Clare Marino/Unsplash.com

The concern of the freedom of media in Bulgaria has been one of the reasons for the start of the demonstrations. According to the Freedom House, the Bulgarian media are not fully free, though pluralistic. Journalists, opposing to the ruling camp, face assault and threats from the government-favourable actors. Also, it is common for the Bulgarian oligarchs to buy opposition media, e.g., Nova TV has been acquired in 2019. Currently, 80 % of the domestic media market belongs to the oligarch Delyan Peevski (Pieńkowski, 2020). Although the media ownership does not impact the immigrants' situation directly, the anti-migration attitudes present in the political discourse can be reflected in the press and television which will negatively influence the public opinion about the immigrants considering that Bulgaria lays on the migration route from Turkey to Western Europe (Freedom House, 2021).

Bulgarian migration policy is determined to participate in the Schengen area, it therefore focuses on securing the EU border and sustaining 'building a fence' pattern. The National Strategy, adopted in 2015, aims at guarding the EU borders and securing from irregular migration, smuggling and trafficking. Migration is comprehended twofold by the policy-makers – as an economic opportunity (legal migrants contribute to the labour force) and as a threat (irregular migrants present in the informal economy). The National Strategy focuses on providing the transparent procedure for the asylum-seekers and balancing between human rights and supporting the national interest (Ivanova, 2018: 6).

Political turmoil is not a favourable ground for receiving immigrants in a large scale. Political instability, if persistent, may strongly influence future migrant inflows. Shortages in the Bulgarian labour market may have catastrophic results for the national economy. In turn, the adopted National Strategy is rather inclusive and may negatively impact many potential immigrants.

Another important factor to discuss is the environment. Bulgaria is located in two climate zones, namely a continental climate in the north and a Mediterranean climate in the south. It is manifested in higher variations in temperature and precipitation in the northern part than in the southern. According to World Bank, Bulgaria will be at climate risk in the following decades. The average temperature is going to rise by 2.2 Celsius degrees until 2060 and the monthly temperature anomalies are projected to appear mostly in the southern areas of the country. At the same time, monthly precipitation is going to decrease by 4.4 mm (World Bank, 2021b). In the light of these forecasts, we may presume that these factors may impact the agricultural sector and result in insufficient food production. However, due to the relatively low risk of floods and droughts (Ibidem) those elements are not probable to highly influence emigration events in the future, especially from the north. On the other hand, Bulgaria lays on the key migratory route and may become a country of transition or settling for climate refugees from Asia and Africa.

7.2 Migration prospects

Even though Bulgaria traditionally has been an emigration country, it shows increased immigration flows after the 1990s. The reasons for it are affordable education, good quality of life and good economic conditions in terms of entrepreneurship and competitiveness of the labour force cost. In 2018, immigrants in Bulgaria, originating mostly from Russia and Ukraine, constituted 1% of the overall population and were concentrated mostly in the capital city – Sofia (Ivanova, 2018: 3-4).

Although the number of Bulgarians has been rising, since 2012 the number of return migrants has been almost a half smaller than the number of Bulgarians leaving their country. For instance, in 2012 nearly 150 persons born in Bulgaria arrived in the country while over 2100 left. The situation changed in favour of the immigration events probably because of implementation of the National Strategy in 2014. Nearly 11 thousand persons arrived and nearly 15 thousand left in 2015 and in 2019 – nearly 22,5 thousand people born in Bulgaria came back and over 37 thousand left (NSI, 2020a). We can presume that this trend of negative net migration rate will remain after the end of the pandemic because of persistent economic instability, possible political perturbations after months of demonstrations and parliamentary change, or a lack of positive political change.

Due to aggregating all EU migrants into one category by the Bulgarian Statistics Office, it is not possible to see the growth or decline of each particular migrant group. To show in our report the share of persons by citizenship, we can only rely on data gathered during the National Census in 2011. Therefore in 2011, the number of European Union citizens in Bulgaria amounted to nearly 8,5 thousand persons (see: Figure 3). At a time, the largest group among EU citizens consisted of the British, which totalled slightly over 2600 persons (over 30% of all the EU citizens living in Bulgaria at a time). According to Ivanova, the British in Bulgaria are mostly so-called retirement migrants and are located in the rural areas of the country (Ivanova, 2018: 3-4). The next largest groups were the Greeks (over 1200 persons), the Germans (nearly 850 persons), the Polish (over 800 persons) and the Italians (over 450 persons) (see: Figure 3).

To construct a wider picture and predict the dynamics of the change of number of EU and non-EU citizens in Bulgaria, we take into account work permits issued. For instance, in 2015 Bulgaria granted and renewed 95 work permits for EU citizens, in 2018 – 285 and in 2020 – 428 (NSI, 2021f). The increasing numbers are a manifestation of attractiveness of Bulgarian labour market for immigrants from the EU. Regarding labour rights, EU citizens are treated like Bulgarian citizens and not like foreigners which guarantees easy access to Bulgarian labour market when it comes to bureaucracy. This group is eagerly hired in call centres because of the English language proficiency (Ivanova, 2018: 3-4).

Bulgaria is competitive with EU states in terms of labour force prices, which reinforce foreign investments. However, low wages do not satisfy highly qualified workers and discourage them to stay in the country. If the trend of lower than EU-average wage level persists, the number of highly qualified EU citizens in Bulgaria on par with Bulgarian citizens will decrease in favour of non-EU citizens (Dimitrov et al., 2019: 78).

The number of non-EU immigrants in Bulgaria totalled 115 000 persons in 2019 (see: Figure 6). Half of them were permanent residence permit holders. The largest group consisted of Russians (nearly 12 thousand persons in 2019), which constituted ca. 65 % of all non-EU country citizens. In 2019 the second largest group were Ukrainian citizens (around 3 thousand persons). Those two migrant groups on par with Belarussians were the most feminized ones among non-EU immigrants. In these three cases, the feminization ratio equalled ca. 80 % (see: Figure 4). Also, Russians and Ukrainians were frequent recipients of residence permits due to family reasons. In 2019, the number of them issued to Russians equated 786 and to Ukrainians – 525, which were constant numbers since 2015 (see: Table 2). We predict that the inflow of members of these two groups may persist in the next three decades on the same level with a chance of increasing because of a high share of permanent stay permits and high feminization rate proving access to the labour market for women.

Another numerous migrant groups in 2011 were Northern Macedonians (ca. 1 thousand persons), Moldovans (nearly 900 persons) and Serbians (over 550 persons) (Ibidem). Unfortunately, we do not acquire accurate data on those specific migrant groups to provide a migration narrative scenario.

In the case of migrants from Asia, the prominent group is Turkish, which constitutes ca. one-third of all Asian-origin migrants in Bulgaria. In the period 2012-2019 Turkish citizens were granted an increasing number of residence permits due to family reasons and a growing feminization rate was observed in the group (see: Figures 6 & 8). Regarding the fact that the number of Turkish citizens has enlarged four times in seven years, we can presume that this trend will prevail in the following decades, especially considering the political aspirations of the Turkish minority in Bulgaria.

An interesting Asian group is the Chinese which in 2011 constituted a share of nearly 9 % of immigrants from Asia arriving in Bulgaria (National Statistical Institute 2011a: 22). Constant but slightly increasing numbers of Chinese citizens have been acquiring residence permits due to family reasons in the previous years. For instance, 91 permits of residence have been issued due to family reasons for Chinese in 2015 and in 2019 – 111. According to Ivanova, Chinese migrants are mostly self-employed (Ivanova, 2018: 3-4). Members of this group tend to hire other newcomers what suggests development of a migration net in Bulgaria (Ibidem). Considering the trend of family linkage and Chinese entrepreneurship skills guaranteeing facilitated economic integration, we may assume that the number of Chinese in Bulgaria will slightly increase in the following three decades but will not grow into large numbers.

In 2016, the USA citizens were the largest group of persons granted residence permits due to work reasons (85 immigrants). In turn, in 2016 the number of residence permits due to family reasons for American citizens totalled 96 and in 2019 - 114 (see: Table 2). Also, relatively new migrants are Indian citizens among which 222 obtained a work permit in 2017. We may presume, that in the following years the share of Americans and Indians in Bulgaria will increase, however number of highly qualified immigrants will not rise significantly in the period of the next three decades if lower than EU-average wage level will persist (Dimitrov et al., 2019: 78).

According to Ivanova, immigration from the Middle East to Bulgaria has a long tradition due to historical relations (Ivanova, 2018: 3). Bulgaria is a destination for migrants from Palestine, Syria, Lebanon, Iraq and Afghanistan. Apart from refugee status holders, members of this group, similar to a few immigrants from Africa, run small family businesses, which guarantee potential migrants new opportunities (Ibidem).

7.3 Asylum-seekers and refugees

Another important point to discuss is receiving refugees. Despite establishing in National Bureau for Territorial Asylum 1993, then renamed to State Agency for Refugees, Bulgaria has never become a key asylum destination because of its social-economic profile (European Commission, 2019).

After 2015, during the so-called migration crisis, Bulgaria became the main transit country for asylum-seekers. Bulgaria did not grant a refugee status or any form of subsidiary protection on a large scale (see: Figure 15 & 16) because of

“The national policy, which puts a strong focus on securing the borders and on a zero-integration policy; the fact of being the poorest country in the EU; the general intention of most of the asylum seekers to reach countries like Germany, Sweden and Western Europe in general; the negative political discourse, and not least, the overall negative attitudes towards refugees from the local population” (Ivanova, 2018: 4)

The number of applicants for refugee status rose dynamically from 1.4 thousand in 2012 to 7.1 thousand in 2013. Then the tendency remained growing as the number of applications in 2014 totalled 11 thousand, in 2015 – 20.3 thousand and in 2016 – 19.4 thousand. The number dramatically dropped in 2017 to 2.6 thousand (Ivanova, 2018: 5). Since then, the number of applications for international protection has been oscillating between 2 thousand and 3 thousand (State Agency for Refugees with the Council of Ministers, 2021). Most of the asylum seekers originated from Afghanistan, Syria, Iraq, Pakistan and Iran (Ivanova, 2018: 6).

Serious acts of discrimination against immigrants and especially refugees were reported in 2017 in Bulgaria. At this time, Bulgarian authorities aimed at limiting the influx of population by increased border control. The border police carried pushbacks, asylum-seekers experienced physical abuse and theft by the border police officers (Amnesty International, 2017: 96-99). On this basis, we can assume that asylum-seekers will not be a major source of demographic influx in the following decades. However, the number of applicants is presumed to rise as a result of military conflicts in developing states and climate change.

7.4 Impact of Covid-19 pandemic

The Covid-19 pandemic had strongly influenced the socio-economic life of Bulgarians and dragged the national market into a recession in 2020. According to World Bank, the poverty level in Bulgaria is projected to increase in 2021 as a result of the job and income losses and rising vulnerabilities associated with the crisis. After the recession, during the recovery phase, the country's key development challenge is a transition to the inclusive market and meeting the average EU income levels. It would help to speed up the productivity gap with the rest of the EU (World Bank, 2021a).

Bulgaria is projected to economically grow and will reach the pre-crisis level in 2022. Also, under the assumption of political stability and high vaccination rates, poverty is projected to decline in 2022 because of an improved economy, favourable labour market conditions and normalized food prices (Ibidem).

References

- "Ponad 2,2 mln Bułgarów żyje za granicą" (2019). Forsal, 3.02, <https://forsal.pl/artykuly/1395781,ponad-22-mln-bulgarow-zyje-za-granica.html>
- Abel, G. J., Cohen, J. E. (2019). Bilateral international migration flow estimates for 200 countries, *Scientific Data*, 6(1), 1-13.
- Angelov, G., Lessenski, M. (2017). 10 years in the EU. Trends in Bulgarian Migration. Open Society Institute Sofia, <https://osis.bg/?p=392&lang=en> (accessed 15.11.2020).
- Bogdanov, G., Rangelova, R. (2012). Social Impact of Emigration and Rural Urban Migration in Central and Eastern Europe, Final Country Report, GVG.
- Brzozowski, J., Chwat, O. (2020). Report on migration and demographic patterns in Poland, FUME project.
- Council of Ministers (2014). National Strategy for Bulgarian Citizens and Historic Bulgarian Communities, adopted with Council of Ministers Decision No. 30.41/23 July 2014.
- Dąbrowski, T. (2014). Citizens of Bulgaria and Romania receive full rights on the EU labour market, OSW, <https://www.osw.waw.pl/en/publikacje/analyses/2014-01-08/citizens-bulgaria-and-romania-receive-full-rights-eu-labour-market> (accessed: 14.12.2020).
- Dimitrov, L., Ganev, K., Vassilev, A. & Simeonova-Ganeva, R. (2019). *Medium-term and long-term forecasts for the development of the labour market in Bulgaria. Employment and labour market imbalances, determinants of labour supply* (2008–2034). European Social Fund.
- Dimitrova, T., & Kahl, T. (2013). "Foreword," in T. Dimitrova and T. Kahl (eds.), *Migration from and towards Bulgaria 1989–2011* (vol. 2), Frank & Timme GmbH, pp. 7-9.
- European Commission. (2019). Governance of Migrant Integration in Bulgaria, <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/governance/bulgaria> (accessed 1.12.2020).
- Eurostat (2015). "Demographic statistics: A review of definitions and methods of collection in 44 European countries", <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/3859598/6851536/KS-GQ-15-002-EN-N/7d6ba1c1-fa04-464b-89ff-ec8796b2db5d>, (accessed 19.12.2020).
- Eurostat (2017). Metadata and quality report on European demographic and migration statistics, Bulgaria, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/EN/demo_pop_esms_bg.htm (accessed 19.12.2020).
- Eurostat. (2021a). *Population on 1 January by age and sex*. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/demo_pjan/default/table?lang=en (accessed 26.07.2021)
- Eurostat. (2021b). *Fertility rates by age*. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/demo_frate/default/table?lang=en (accessed 26.07.2021)

- Freedom House, (2021). Bulgaria. <https://freedomhouse.org/country/bulgaria/freedom-world/2021> (accessed 12.09.2021)
- Guentcheva, R., Kabakchieva, P., Kolarski, P. (2003). "The social impact of seasonal migration", in: *Sharing Experience: Migration Trends in Selected Applicant, Countries and Lessons Learned from the 'New Countries of Immigration' in the EU and Austria*, IOM
- European Commission Project (2003). Volume I: Bulgaria, https://publications.iom.int/system/files/pdf/migrationtrends_eu_1.pdf
- IOM (2016). Bulgaria, <https://www.iom.int/countries/bulgaria> (accessed 18.11.2020).
- Ivanova, V. (2018). *The wages of fear: Attitudes towards refugees and migrants in Bulgaria*. Empowering Communities in Europe Report.
- Koch, S. (2020). The formation of Bulgaria's policy concerning Bulgarians abroad, International Centre for Ethnic and Linguistic Diversity Studies, <https://www.icelds.org/2020/01/27/the-formation-of-bulgarias-policy-concerning-bulgarians-abroad/> (accessed 5.11.2020).
- Koyama, Y. (2018). Migration from New EU Member States in Central and Eastern Europe and Their Depopulation: Case of Bulgaria, *Historical Studies of Socialist System*, No. 4.
- Krasteva, A. (2006). Post-communist discovery of immigration: the case of Bulgaria. *SEER-South-East Europe Review for Labour and Social Affairs*, (02), 25-34.
- Krasteva, A. (2019). The Bulgarian Migration Paradox. *Migration and Development in Bulgaria*, Common Home series, Caritas Bulgaria, <https://www.caritas.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/CommonHomeBulgariaEN.pdf>
- Minority Rights Group. (2018a). *Bulgaria*. <https://minorityrights.org/country/bulgaria/>, (accessed 27.07.2021)
- Minority Rights Group. (2018b). *Bulgaria. Turks*. <https://minorityrights.org/minorities/turks-2/>, (accessed 28.07.2021)
- Minority Rights Group. (2018c). *Bulgaria. Roma*. <https://minorityrights.org/minorities/roma-2/>, (accessed 28.07.2021)
- National Statistical Institute (2011a). 2011 Population Census in the Republic of Bulgaria (final data), Available at: https://www.nsi.bg/census2011/PDOCS2/Census2011final_en.pdf (accessed: 02.12.2020).
- National Statistical Institute (2011b). Population and housing census in the Republic of Bulgaria 2011, Available at: <https://www.nsi.bg/census2011/pageen2.php?p2=179&sp2=209> (accessed: 02.12.2020).
- National Statistical Institute (2020a). International migration by citizenship - total for the country, Available at: https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/module.jsf?x_2=38 (accessed: 07.12.2020).
- National Statistical Institute (2020b). Private communication via email (dates: 22.10.2020- 19.12.2020).
- National Statistical Institute (2020c). Population by citizenship, age and sex, Available at: https://infostat.nsi.bg/infostat/pages/module.jsf?x_2=80 (accessed: 07.12.2020).

- National Statistical Institute (2020d). Third-country nationals holders of long-term/permanent residence as of 31.12., Available at: <https://www.nsi.bg/en/content/16335/third-country-nationals-holders-long-termpermanent-residence-3112> (accessed: 21.12.2020).
- National Statistical Institute (2020e). Population and Demographic Processes 2019, <https://www.nsi.bg/en/content/18560/публикация/population-and-demographic-processes-2019> (accessed 20.12.2020).
- National Statistical Institute (2020f). Methodology on statistics of residence permits, https://www.nsi.bg/sites/default/files/files/metadata/Pop_5.2_Methodology_RESPER_en.pdf (accessed 23.12.2020).
- National Statistical Institute, Metadata and Methodology, <https://www.nsi.bg/en/content/6683/migration> (accessed 10.12.2020).
- National Statistical Institute, Methodology on Statistics and Residence Permits, https://www.nsi.bg/sites/default/files/files/metadata/Pop_5.2_Methodology_RESPER_en.pdf (accessed 20.12.2020).
- National Statistical Institute. (2021a). Population and demographic processes in 2019. https://www.nsi.bg/sites/default/files/files/pressreleases/Population2019_en_XE8MEZL.pdf, (accessed 27.07.2021).
- National Statistical Institute. (2021e). Employed and employment rates of population aged 15 years and over <https://www.nsi.bg/en/content/6500/employed-and-employment-rates-national-level-statistical-regions-districts> (accessed 26/07.2021)
- National Statistical Institute. Methodology for Studying of Migration, https://www.nsi.bg/sites/default/files/files/metadata/Pop_5_Metodology_migration_en.pdf (accessed 5.12.2020).
- National Statistical Institute. (2021a). *Deaths by districts, municipalities and sex.* <https://www.nsi.bg/en/content/6631/deaths-districts-municipalities-and-sex> (accessed 26.07.2021)
- National Statistical Institute. (2021b). *Mortality and life expectancy by sex and place of residence.* <https://www.nsi.bg/en/content/6643/mortality-and-life-expectancy-sex-and-place-residence> (accessed 26.07.2021)
- National Statistical Institute. (2021c). *International migration by age and sex.* <https://www.nsi.bg/en/content/6697/international-migration-age-and-sex> (accessed 26.07.2021)
- National Statistical Institute (2020d). *Residence permits granted during the year to third country nationals by reasons and length of validity.* <https://www.nsi.bg/en/content/16331/residence-permits-granted-during-year-third-country-nationals-reasons-and-length> (accessed 26.07.2021)
- National Statistical Institute. (2021f). *EU Blue Cards issued and renewed in accordance with Directive 2009/50/EC.* <https://www.nsi.bg/en/content/16337/eu-blue-cards-issued-and-renewed-accordance-directive-2009-50-ec> (accessed 28.10.2021)
- OECD. (2021a). *Economic Assessment of Bulgaria 2021.* <https://www.oecd.org/economy/surveys/bulgaria-2021-OECD-economic-survey-overview.pdf>, (accessed 26.07.2021)

- OECD. (2021b). *Economic Policy Reforms 2021*. <https://www.oecd.org/economy/growth/Bulgaria-country-note-going-for-growth-2021.pdf>, (accessed 27.07.2021)
- Open Society Institute (2017). *Migration Trends in Bulgaria, 10 Years in EU*, https://osis.bg/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/MigrationTrendsBulgaria_10YearEU_EuPI_Oct_2017_EN.pdf (accessed: 10.12.2020).
- Pieńkowski, J. (2020). *Antyrządowe protesty w Bułgarii*. The Polish Institute of National Affairs. https://www.pism.pl/publikacje/Antyrzadowe_protesty_w_Bulgarii, (accessed 13.08.2021)
- Savova, I. (2020). *Country report: Bulgaria, Asylum Information Database, European Council on Refugees and Exiles*, <https://www.asylumineurope.org/reports/country/bulgaria> (accessed: 21.12.2020).
- Seroka, M. (2021). *Bułgaria: powyborcze pogłębienie kryzysu politycznego*. *Centre for Eastern Studies*. <https://www.osw.waw.pl/pl/publikacje/analizy/2021-07-13/bulgaria-powyborcze-poglabienie-kryzysu-politycznego>, (accessed 6.08.2021)
- Smilov, D., & Jileva, E. (2009). *The politics of Bulgarian citizenship: National identity, democracy, and other uses*. In R. Bauböck, B. Perchinig, & W. Sievers (Eds.), *Citizenship policies in the new Europe* (pp. 211–248). Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press.
- State Agency for Refugees with the Council of Ministers (2020a). *Number of applicants for international protection and decisions taken in the period 1993 – 2020*, Available at: <http://www.aref.government.bg/index.php/en/node/179> (accessed: 21.12.2020).
- State Agency for Refugees with the Council of Ministers (2020b). *Top 5 asylum seeker countries of origin 01.01.1993 – 31.12.2019*, Available at: http://www.aref.government.bg/sites/default/files/uploads/docs/2020-03/1%20-%20Top%205-english_12.pdf (accessed: 21.12.2020).
- State Agency for Refugees with the Council of Ministers. (2021). *Number of applicants for international protection and decisions taken in the period 1993-2021.June*. <https://www.aref.government.bg/index.php/en/node/179>, (accessed at 20.07.2021)
- Vankova, Z. (2020). *Diaspora Policies, Consular Services and Social Protection for Bulgarian Citizens Abroad*, in: J.M. Lafleur, D. Vintila (eds.), *Migration and Social Protection in Europe and Beyond* (Vol. 2). *Comparing Consular Services and Diaspora Policies*, Springer, pp. 69-89.
- World Bank. (2021a). *Bulgaria. Country Overview*. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/bulgaria/overview>, (accessed 27.07.2021)
- World Bank. (2021b). *Bulgaria. Climate projections*. <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/bulgaria/climate-data-projections> (accessed 25.08.2021)

